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● ***Dipoenoides* Chamberlin, 1925 is the valid name for the genus *Emertonella* Bryant, 1945 (Araneae, Theridiidae, Hadrotarsinae)**

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● **拟圆腹蛛属是埃蛛属的有效名称（蜘蛛目，球蛛科，哈多蛛亚科）**

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Euryopsis Menge, 1868 is the second most diverse genus of the subfamily Hadrotarsinae Thorell, 1881 (Hu *et al.* 2026; World Spider Catalog 2026). Levi (1954) and Levi & Levi (1962) revised this genus and proposed several synonyms, including *Acanthomysmena* Mello-Leitão, 1944, *Dipoenoides* Chamberlin, 1925, *Emertonella* Bryant, 1945, *Mufila* Bryant, 1949, among others. Yoshida (2002) revalidated *Emertonella* and noted that “all the species of the *Eu. emertoni* group designed by Levi (1954) belong to this genus”, but did not formally transfer the species. Hu *et al.* (2026) formally transferred all species of the *Eu. emertoni* group, together with 16 additional species, to *Emertonella*, including *Em. scriptipes* (Banks, 1908), the type species of *Dipoenoides*. However, because *Dipoenoides* has priority over *Emertonella*, the use of the latter generic name by Hu *et al.* (2026) renders it invalid under the Principle of Priority (ICZN 1999: Art. 23). The aims of the current paper are to revalidate *Dipoenoides* and to transfer 35 species currently placed in *Emertonella* to *Dipoenoides*.

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Order Araneae Clerck, 1757 蜘蛛目

Infraorder Araneomorphae Smith, 1892 新蛛下目

Family Theridiidae Sundevall, 1833 球蛛科

Subfamily Hadrotarsinae Thorell, 1881 哈多蛛亚科

Genus *Dipoenoides* Chamberlin, 1925 gen. rest. 拟圆腹蛛属

Dipoenoides Chamberlin, 1925: 215 (considered a junior synonym of *Euryopsis* by Levi 1954: 3; type species *D. apacheus* Chamberlin, 1925 considered a junior synonym of *Eu. scriptipes* Banks, 1908 by Levi 1954: 43, transferred to *Emertonella* by Hu *et al.* 2006: 287). **gen. rest.**

Acanthomysmena Mello-Leitão, 1944: 323 (considered a junior synonym of *Euryopsis* by Levi & Levi 1962: 15; type species *A. spinifera* Mello-Leitão, 1944, transferred to *Emertonella* by Hu *et al.* 2006: 288).

Emertonella Bryant, 1945: 182 (considered a junior synonym of *Euryopsis* by Levi 1954: 3, revalidated by Yoshida 2002: 17; type species *Em. emertoni* Bryant, 1933). **syn. nov.**

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Mufila Bryant, 1949: 66 (considered a junior synonym of *Euryopsis* by Levi 1954: 3; type species *M. texana* Bryant, 1949 considered a junior synonym of *Eu. quinque maculata* Banks, 1900 by Levi 1963: 131, transferred to *Emertonella* by Hu *et al.* 2006: 287).

Type species. *Dipoenoides scriptipes* (Banks, 1908) **comb. rest.**

Diagnosis and description. See Hu *et al.* (2026) under *Emertonella*.

Composition. 35 species are herein transferred from *Emertonella* **syn. nov.:** *Dipoenoides boliviensis* (Rodrigues, Marta & Figueiredo, 2021) **comb. nov.**, *D. californica* (Banks, 1904) **comb. nov.**, *D. camis* (Levi, 1963) **comb. nov.**, *D. catarinensis* (Rodrigues, Marta & Figueiredo, 2021) **comb. nov.**, *D. cobreensis* (Levi, 1963) **comb. nov.**, *D. coki* (Levi, 1954) **comb. nov.**, *D. cyclosisa* (Zhu & Song, 1997) **comb. nov.**, *D. deplanata* (Schenkel, 1936) **comb. nov.**, *D. emertoni* (Bryant, 1933) **comb. nov.**, *D. emiliae* (Lecigne, 2023) **comb. nov.**, *D. episinoides* (Walckenaer, 1847) **comb. nov.**, *D. formosa* (Banks, 1908) **comb. nov.**, *D. funebris* (Hentz, 1850) **comb. nov.**, *D. lineatipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1893) **comb. nov.**, *D. mallah* (Zakerzade, Moradmand & Jäger, 2022) **comb. nov.**, *D. mulaiki* (Levi, 1954) **comb. nov.**, *D. nasuta* (Rodrigues, Marta & Figueiredo, 2021) **comb. nov.**, *D. nigra* (Yoshida, 2000) **comb. nov.**, *D. pepini* (Levi, 1954) **comb. nov.**, *D. pickardi* (Levi, 1963) **comb. nov.**, *D. quinqueguttata* (Thorell, 1875) **comb. nov.**, *D. quinque maculata* (Banks, 1900) **comb. nov.**, *D. scriptipes* (Banks, 1908) **comb. rest.**, *D. serrulata* (Gao & Li, 2014) **comb. nov.**, *D. sexmaculata* (Hu, 2001) **comb. nov.**, *D. spinifera* (Mello-Leitão, 1944) **comb. nov.**, *D. spinigera* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1895) **comb. nov.**, *D. spiritus* (Levi, 1954) **comb. nov.**, *D. taczanowskii* (Keyserling, 1886) **comb. nov.**, *D. talaveraensis* (González, 1991) **comb. nov.**, *D. tavana* (Levi, 1954) **comb. nov.**, *D. texana* (Banks, 1908) **comb. nov.**, *D. trachypa* (Gao & Li, 2014) **comb. nov.**, *D. varis* (Levi, 1963) **comb. nov.**, and *D. weesei* (Levi, 1963) **comb. nov.**

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● Additional information

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